

Energy efficiency assessment through drone-based technology in industrial environments

Lario J¹, Mateos J¹, Poler R¹, Ortiz A¹

Abstract This paper presents an investigation into the assessment of industrial energy efficiency during maintenance operations utilizing unmanned aerial vehicles or drones. It compares traditional inspection methods performed by operators with automated data collection carried out by drones. The aim is to enhance data response time and automation, therefore preventing potential energy losses. In addition, this approach provides Operations and Maintenance operators safer working conditions and accessible real-time updated data, empowering them to execute maintenance tasks and make informed decisions to prevent equipment failures.

Keywords: Energy Efficiency; Performance; Drones; Cost; Manual Labor.

1 Introduction

The European Union (EU) has witnessed a significant growth in the development and deployment of photovoltaic (PV) installations during the last decades, providing a shift in the energy generation market. This has been possible due to multitude of factors including higher efficiency PV modules (increased from 9% in 1980 to 14.7% in 2010 and 20.9% in 2021) [1], reduced cost in PV module installations, and supportive policies [2] [3] and incentives [4] promoted by the EU authorities. Energy consumption is an important part of the costs that affect the production and final price of manufactured products within the European Union. Industrial facilities energy consumption contributed in 2021 to 25.6% of the total energy consumption in Europe [5], of which 33.2% corresponded to electricity consumption [6]. In addition to these facts, there is an existing need for electricity in industrial processes and operations, mainly attributed to two factors: the ongoing Ukraine-Russia conflict, resulting in a natural gas supply shortage, and the ongoing efforts from the European Union's on the ambitious target of achieving net carbon emissions by 2050 [7] which is the objective behind the EU Green Deal [8]. Therefore, industries

¹Joan Lario Femenía, Javier Mateos Luengo, Raúl Poler Escoto Ángel Ortiz Bas (e-mail: jlario@cigip.upv.es; jamaule@cigip.upv.es; rpoler@cigip.upv.es; aortiz@cigip.upv.es)
Research Centre on Production Management and Engineering (CIGIP), Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera S/N, 46022 València, Spain

have transitioned towards more sustainable energy production methods such as solar PV energy which helps to achieve more sustainable production methods cost-effectively. Over the last few decades, the installed capacity of photovoltaic power has increased considerably up to 270 GW and is projected to increase to 720 GW by 2030 [1]. Many of the installations contributing to this capacity increase have been located on the rooftops and roofs of these industrial facilities, allowing them to considerably reduce their energy bills. However, most of these PV solar installations are located in areas that are not very accessible for the technicians to review, such as solar roofs or canopies, which makes it dangerous and hard to maintain during their lifecycle. Within this context and due to the growing development of remote sensors, high-resolution imagery and the use of unmanned aerial systems (UAS), an autonomous system for the inspection of industrial roofs based on infrared thermal imaging is proposed.

2 Methodology and Use case

In recent years, the use of drones for industrial inspections has gained considerable attention due to their ability to provide efficient, versatile and inexpensive inspections. These advancements linked with high-quality remote sensing equipment enable the effectiveness of drone-based inspections when compared to traditional methods typically used for assessing the performance of electrical installations [9]. In the proposed use case, the thermal infrared (IR) inspections conducted in a heavy boiler making factory, where a renewable photovoltaic (PV) solar installation of 7.923 m² and roughly 1 MWp of solar energy capacity is located on the rooftop of the industrial warehouse. To evaluate the condition of the solar installation, a UAS flight is proposed with an infrared sensor that receives the emissivity of the solar panels and makes it possible to locate the hot spots of a potentially defective module. The IR sensor mounted in the drone was an uncooled VOx microbolometer able to measure temperatures in the range of -20 up to 500 °C with an accuracy less than 50 mK and an image resolution of 640x512 pixels. To perform the data acquisition correctly, several technical aspects must be considered such as the reflection of external elements on the solar modules or the flight altitude of the UAS can directly affect the image collection process. However, the most important parameter to consider is the angle of inspection relative to the position between the infrared sensor and the PV module inclination. This must be set to minimize the recirculation of hot air towards the upper part of the module, which can lead to false positives [10]. Therefore the drone gimbal angle (α_1) must be set to the same value as the inclination of the PV module installation (α_2) and the field of view (FOV) of the IR sensor must be greater than the module length (L) and width (W) for an adequate IR data collection [Figure 1].

The minimum flight height is defined according to the required FOV, which in our case is the size of a PV module with a length of 1.75m by 1m wide. Therefore, any flight above 2.75m altitude will capture the entire solar module as per Table 1.

Fig. 1 Angle Parameters for Data Collection.

When using remote sensing devices at different flight heights, Ground Sample Distance (GSD) parameter must be considered. GSD refers to the physical size of one pixel in the ground when an image is captured by a remote sensing device, its calculation is based on the sensor resolution, size and altitude. This parameter allows us to obtain the maximum flight height that allows us to identify anomalies and pixel patterns in solar modules while reducing the inspection time on the UAS. By selecting a flight altitude of 20m, the potential defects to be identified have a minimum pixel size of 0.27cm.

Table 1. GSD and FOV based on flight altitude.

Flight Height [m]	GSD [cm/pixel]	FOV [m]
2.75	0.27	1.75 x 1.40
5	0.50	3.18 x 2.54
10	1	6.35 x 5.08
15	1.49	9.53 x 7.62
20	1.98	12.7 x 10.16

With all the parameters defined both the sensor configuration and drone altitude navigation, the designated solar PV area to be inspected is delineated. For this purpose, the use of open-source software for remote flight programming QGroundControl [11], is used. This software enables the programming of UAV flights [12], initiating the data acquisition process.

3 Data Analysis

There are many reasons why an electrical installation may lose efficiency over the years. Some of them are related to the degradation of the solar panels themselves and external climatic phenomena such as hailstorms, accumulated dirt or internal electrical failures of the modules [13]. PV module degradation causes overheating which results in potential solar panel failure and minimizes output power that affects the long-term reliability of the solar installation. Image analysis with infrared thermography is a reliable, non-destructive, and cost-effective technique that makes possible to detect hot spots and degraded areas thanks to the thermal contrast detected by infrared sensors. The use of this type of technology has received a great deal of attention in recent years and linked to the development of machine vision models makes it even more attractive as the processing and inference of these images can be automated [14]. These characteristics provide a high degree of

automation and scalability, providing O&M teams with new tools for the inspection of assets such as the contribution of renewable energy to the product manufacturing supply chain.

3.1 Data Acquisition, Preparation and Inference

Data acquisition for the training of machine vision models for anomaly detection is based on the collection of infrared images of the electrical installation located on the roof. These images are captured at a height of 20 m above the location of the solar panels and with vertical and horizontal overlap parameters of 90% and 70% respectively. The flight time of the inspection takes approximately 25 minutes to complete while collecting a total of 1352 images with four spectral bands RGB + IR [Figure 2 left].

Fig. 2. Flight Route on QGroundControl (left) and Solar PV Reconstruction (right).

Using the RGB images from the drone and photogrammetry techniques, the rooftop solar installation of the facility is reconstructed. This image serves as a base map or reference [Figure 2 right] for the representation of the anomalies detected in the installation, allowing the O&M team to locate the affected modules more accurately and efficiently. With the help of image annotators such as VGG Annotator or Roboflow and the use of pre-trained computer vision weights on PV anomalies an inference server for anomaly detection is created. The computer vision algorithm pre-trained is based on the popular object detector You Only Look Once (YOLO) model [15] and can be re-trained using custom drone image datasets. Once the inference server is ready for deployment, the anomaly detection is run on a NVIDIA 4050 GPU detecting a total of 31 anomalies in PV solar modules 3 which accounts for a potential loss of power of 12.4kWp. This could result on a monthly cost of 1,230€/month based on the average electricity price for industrial consumers of 0.2064€/kWh [16]. This extra energy demand from the grid has impacted the overall cost of the final product.

Fig. 3. Types of anomalies detected in the PV installation.

3.2 Data Visualization

Once the inference is run on the thermal images in the solar installation, all the images with anomalies detected and their metadata containing latitude and longitude parameters collected in the UAV flights are used for data representation. With the drone's positioning system and the bounding box location from the detection algorithm, anomalies are automatically identified and geographically referenced, providing the exact module location, and electrical fault type to maintenance operators for future repair or replacement [Figure 3]. Once the exact location where anomalies are detected, an interactive map is created [Figure 4] to provide O&M teams with up-to-date information and accurate PV module location. This information is used to take corrective action in a coordinated way to improve the efficiency of the installation while reducing the inspection time it would take operators to manually walk around the solar roof with a thermal camera with the added risk that these actions entail.

Fig. 4. Anomalies detected in the roof.

4 Conclusions and Future Steps

The early identification and mitigation of PV anomalies within an industrial context is essential to mitigate energy efficiency losses due to solar module degradation. This paper proposes a systematic workflow designed to automate the entire inspection process, including data acquisition, analysis and visualization. Streamlining the updated data is essential to coordinate subsequent corrective maintenance actions. It is widely acknowledged that the lack of preventive and corrective actions not performed on time in the facility has an impact on the energy cost associated with the process. Therefore, delays in corrective actions are significantly harmful in scenarios where processes consume vast amounts of energy, such as the submerged arc welding (SAW) process which is an essential part of the use-case scenario. As a result of the malfunction in the renewable solar energy installation, there is an increase in daily production energy demand from the grid, increasing the direct costs associated to the process in terms of energy consumption.

The continuous degradation of the solar installation is inevitable over time, mostly due to the lifetime of these installations, which is around 25-30 years [13]. It is therefore advisable to follow maintenance guidelines with an appropriate frequency that allows the inspection of these assets in an easy, simple and intuitive way. Future lines of research will focus on the implementation of more efficient detection methods that not only rely on aerial thermography but also on techniques such as electroluminescence [17]. In addition, the possible improvement of other technical aspects such as fully autonomous flights or the incorporation of routing algorithms to

identify the optimal route to follow for the repair process on the roof is also being considered.

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